

**CHARACTERISTICS OF FUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN THE
CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM IN CHILDREN WITH RECURRENT CH I
BRONCHITIS AND PROLONGED CH I Y FEVER.**

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Sign in. Young in children breath get pathology with illness children of pulmonology important from problems one being remains, breath get system diseases organs and functional disorders of systems with passing , eng less studied , breath get with closely depends has been and body with oxygen in providing directly participation which heart-blood vein system h am attraction q suspension with passing disease being remains.

Research purpose: long continue which cough with passing recurring with bronchitis in children heart-blood vein functional changes in the system features study.

Materials and research methods . We right now of life in the first 3 years Diagnosis of recurrent bronchitis (RB). with , babies in the department 45 people lying down bedridden patient with recurrent bronchitis the children We checked , 25 of them are under 1 year old, 12 are under 2 years old and 8 under 3 years of age has been children _ Children It was studied in 2 groups. 1st group - heart in ECG examinations change with Recurrent bronchitis was detected - 30 cases, 2 groups and the heart in ECG examinations change you are going through Recurrent bronchitis was detected in 15 children observed. 28 of the children under investigation son and 17 are girls . To realize the goal again Clinical - anamnestic , functional and instrumental (ECG E C XOCG) examinations , narrow specialists consultations (ENT, neuropathologist, ophthalmologist.) and taken from parents from questionnaires

Results and discussions. As a result of the study, in 37 children , ante- and intranatal of hypoxia combination note done 15% of the children in the study died in term born but the body weight is low, i.e. 2200-2500 g, 15% with a higher body weight, i.e. 3300-3500 g. 65% of children from term i before born , 3 of them. 1200-1500 which is very low weight g. Electrocardiographic information in learning heart-blood vein system different level of functional disorders symptoms were detected in children of the 1st group - 90.2% of cases . In children heart-blood vein functional disorders of the system main signs (86.4%), " marbling " of the skin (84.7%), heart change of muffled sounds (37.3%) to accentuation (30.5%) , bradycardia (23.7%) and tachycardia

(22.0%), arrhythmia (22.0%) and myocardial ventricular repolarization violation (100%) was observed. Rhythm and of conductivity violation new born complete term 85.7 percent of infants and early born in 80 percent of infants perinatal central nerve system damage with observed . Belly extrasystole only early born 4 is in the gills observed. Disorders of the structure of cardiac arrhythmias are as follows: sinus tachycardia or arrhythmia - 25, sinus bradycardia - 6, extrasystole -3, supraventricular paroxysmal tachycardia - 3, ectopic rhythm - 2, sinus node weakness syndrome -1, syndrome - WPW - 1, atrioventricular block - 1 observed in a child. In 2/3 of children, depression of the ST segment, inversion, and a decrease in the amplitude of the T wave were noted, which was observed to be expressed more strongly in children of the early neonatal period.

Conclusion. Signs of various levels of functional disorders of the cardiovascular system were detected in 90.2% of children of the 1st group. Disease in children heart-blood vein functional disorders of the system main signs with . Rhythm and conduction disorders were observed in 85.7% of full-term newborns and 80% of premature babies with damage to the perinatal central nervous system. Therefore, the autonomous regulation of heart rate in children today remains an urgent problem not only for pediatricians, but also for narrow specialists in general.

